

From: American Journal of Biomedical Science & Research <agri@biomedgrid.org>
To: Mattan Schlomi <mattanschlomi@aol.com>
Cc: mshelomi@ntu.edu.tw <mshelomi@ntu.edu.tw>
Subject: RE: Acceptance for Publication: AG-MRW-19-0545
Date: Sat, Dec 7, 2019 1:17 pm

Dear Dr. Schlomi Mattan,

Hope this email finds you in good spirit.

We kindly remind you regarding the payment process of **\$1179** to activate DOI number. So, kindly process the amount through the below URL and forward the receipt for confirmation. Please track the below link to make online payment

<https://biomedgrid.com/pay-online.php>

Hope this least contribution is not a big deal to eminent people like you.

Please acknowledge this mail within 24 hours.

Await your optimistic response.

Regards,

Catherine Nichols

American Journal of Biomedical Science & Research | ISSN: 2642-1747